

IN ENGLISH, THE PHENOMENON OF DEONYMIZATION (TRANSITION OF
PROPER NOUNS TO COMMON NOUNS)

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Abstract. This article first briefly discusses the ways in which the vocabulary system of the English language is enriched. Then, it introduces what nouns are in the linguistics of English, their types, and the phenomenon of deonymization that occurs in the noun phrase. The article gives examples for deonymization, examples are obtained from available sources.

Keywords: noun phrase, proper nouns, common nouns, deonymization phenomenon, vocabulary system, word formation, Shakespeare, onema, prefix, root.

В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ ДЕОНИМИЗАЦИИ (ПЕРЕХОД ИМЕНИ СОБСТВЕННОГО В НАПАДНОЕ)

Абстракт. В данной статье сначала кратко рассматриваются пути обогащения словарной системы английского языка. Затем он знакомит с тем, что такое существительные в лингвистике английского языка, их типы и явление деонимизации, которое происходит в именной группе. В статье приведены примеры для деонимизации, примеры получены из доступных источников.

Ключевые слова: именная группа, имена нарицательные, родственные существительные, феномен деонимизации, система лексики, словообразование, Шекспир, онема, приставка, корень.

INGLIZ TILIDA DEONIMIZATSIYA (ATOQLI OTLARNING TURDOSH OTGA O'TISHI) HODISASI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola avvalo ingliz tilidagi lug'at sistemasining qanday usullarda boyib borayotgani haqida qisqacha so'z yuritadi. So'ngra, ingliz tilida otlar nima ekanligi, ularning turlari va ot so'z turkumida sodir bo'ladigan deonimizatsiya hodisasini tanishtiradi va bu bo'yicha ingliz tilida namunalar keltiradi. Namunalar asosli manbalardan olinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ot so'z turkumi, atoqli otlar, turdosh otlar, deonimizatsiya hodisasi, lug'at sistemasi, so'z yasalishi, Shekspir, onema, old qo'shimcha, so'z asosi.

INTRODUCTION

The processes of deonymization of proper names of various types are at the center of great interest among linguists for a number of disciplines, such as theoretical and practical translation, the history of language development, linguoculturology. Having its own national and cultural specific features, deonymization is widely reflected in many languages and cultures of the world at various stages of their formation. The study of this process makes it possible to penetrate deeper into the peculiarities and specifics of the cultural background of native speakers of a particular language, to use vocabulary more widely for applied purposes, in educational and pedagogical practice, in courses on general lexicology, onomastics and terminology.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Language does not have any limit as it continues to develop and renew day by day. And certainly, the most dynamic level of the language is vocabulary. Because people use the vocabulary of a language more frequently than the grammar of the language. For non-linguistic people, a language is considered to be its vocabulary.

As [dictionary publishers never tire](#) of [reminding us](#), our language is growing. Not content with the million or so words they already have at their disposal, English speakers are adding new vocabularies at the rate of around 1,000 a year. Recent dictionary debutants include blog, grok, crowdfunding, hackathon, airball, e-marketing, sudoku, twerk and Brexit.

But these represent just a sliver of the tip of the iceberg. According to Global [Language](#) Monitor, around 5,400 new words are created every year; it's only the 1,000 or so deemed to be in sufficiently widespread use that make it into print. Who invents these words, and how? What rules govern their formation?

For example, Shakespeare is often held up as a master neologist, because at least 500 words (including critic, swagger, lonely and hint) first appear in his works – but we have no way of knowing whether he personally invented them or was just transcribing things he had picked up somewhere.

However, not only Shakespeare, although common people who are not related to the linguistic field are not aware of linguistic terms, such as onyms, nouns, deonymization; it is they who often create some new words or multiple-meaning words in the language.

Thanks to some linguists' opinion, the question "how are new words born in the language?" can be replies like this:

All new words are created by one of some lingual mechanisms, such as derivation, repurposing, conversion, eponyms, deonymization and other types.

Here, the discussion is given about some words that came across deonymization. First of all, what is deonymization?

Nouns are divided into two types:

Common nouns and proper nouns.

- Proper nouns are nouns which mean specific people, things, and places that are named after. They are always written with capital letters.

- Common nouns are more general than proper ones. They name generic types of people, things, and places. They are normally only capitalized at the start of a sentence.

Deonymization is linguistically explained in the following way:

Prefix **de-** means "off" or "from that has a negative meaning in any kind of word that it is added, onyma (ónoma is derived from greek root) is a name. we can conclude from this that deonymization is the rule of losing properness of nouns and their usage as common nouns.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

You may recognise Alzheimer's, atlas, cheddar, alsatian, diesel, sandwich, mentor, svengali, wellington and boycott as eponyms – but did you know that gun, dunce, bigot, bugger, cretin, currant, hooligan, marmalade, maudlin, maverick, panic, silhouette, syphilis, tawdry, doggerel, doily and sideburns are too?

When a proper name becomes a common noun, "it is filled with a new meaning that correlates with the typical activity of the named person, with typical products, with any characteristic conditions of the area, and others. This process is commonly called deonymization. As a result of the deonymization process, a large number of new words

arise, and these words can differ significantly from each other, both in their structure and in the scope of their usage.

Deonymization can occur both naturally and artificially. In the natural way, it proceeds gradually and may be incomplete.

For example, **Eve**:

1) a female name; according to legend, the first woman was called by this name; for example: *Adam and Eve, according to the fable, wore the bower before other clothes.*

2) as her name is rich in symbolism, characterizing her archetypal role: as the first woman, Eve represents **the essential life-giving maternal function of women**. Archetypal maternal authority is also implied in her role as name-giver of the first human child, in short it means seductress, **"living one" or "source of life"**.

For example: *Eve is the best person you will ever meet, and she will be your best friend forever. You are really lucky if you have a Eve as a girlfriend sister family member or even bestie. Eve will always be there to be your supporter and will give you the best hugs.* (from Urban dictionary)

Adam:

1) the first man, according to the Old Testament; banished from paradise for violating the prohibitions that existed in it;

for example: *The narrator assumes that Adam and Eve had an innate faculty of speech.*

2) the male name of many peoples, both Christians and Muslims or Adam is the common noun in Hebrew for “human(-kind)”;

for example: *adam, come up!*

Solomon:

1) a male name; it was the name of one of the ancient kings, distinguished by great wisdom;

For example: *One day, King Solomon was sitting on his throne, and his great men were standing around him.*

2) a wise man, it is often used to talk about a very wise person

For example: *In this job you need to exhibit the wisdom of Solomon.*

Such proper names, saturated with additional meanings, are easily included in various kinds of "winged" expressions, stable turns of speech: Eve the seductress, King Solomon and all his wisdom, Adam, Adam's apple (forbidden fruit), Adam's rib, from which Eve came out, and others.

In these cases, the names Eve and Solomon were not fully appealed. The first and main purpose of their "being proper names" remains, as indicated by the initial capital letter. However, they were strongly pushed by the above connotations, thanks to which Adam, Eve and Solomon now mean not just people, but people of a certain mindset or character.

If the transition of proper names into common nouns is carried out "artificially", or sometimes purposefully and intentionally, then this transition can be simultaneous, and the words Newton (unit of mass), Curie (unit of radioactivity), Ohm (unit of resistance) become homonyms of proper names Newton, Curie, Ohm. Along with this, a kind of synonymous series consists of phrases with the original name: Ohm's law, Lomonosov–Lavoisier law, Down's disease. Here proper names seem to remain by themselves, but the whole combination as a whole falls into new linguistic conditions – into the ranks of terminological combinations and nomenclature designations.

For people of different countries and different cultures, there may be their own national specifics in the set of names. For example, the most common name in the past in England, **Jack**, began to denote a man with a low social status, especially a servant, a peasant, a sailor.

For example: *"He calls the knaves, jacks, this boy. (From "Great expectations)*

Or the English name **Hans** means a German or a Dane,

For example: *Last week he said you brought him two cinnamon tornados from Hans's bakery.*

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the role of the phenomena of deonimization and transonimization in the process of nouns in the linguistic nature is of great interest for linguists in any language, especially in the English language, which is considered to be the world

language, used more than any other languages of the world. Deonymization helps people to realize the inner side of linguistics and national identities, religious beliefs of a country and its people, as well.

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